

THE CARPENTRIES

2023 Carpentries Community Survey Evaluation Report

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Introduction

The Carpentries is supported by our growing international community, which is vital to accomplishing our mission as well as the functioning of the organisation. It is difficult to quantify the exact size of our community because there are many ways to participate that we are not yet able to count. That being said, here are a few statistics. We have over 4,300 certified Instructors, 4,394 individuals in our Slack workspace, 2,920 subscribers to our monthly newsletter, and 4,948 email addresses registered to one or more of our mailing lists. These numbers do not speak to how many are currently actively engaged; however, internal changes to the AMY database will hopefully make this possible in the future.

Evaluation Methods

Our community survey was guided by desired outcomes for community building outlined in The Carpentries Theory of Change (Appendix A). We specifically wanted to address the following evaluation questions:

- How are community members currently engaging with the organisation? What motivates them to engage?
- How can we improve the volunteer experience?
- Are community members satisfied with the tools available to support them?
- How can we facilitate community reciprocity, providing opportunities for community members to learn from the community while also sharing their expertise?
- What work should the Core Team prioritise to better support the community over the next year?

To address these questions, an online survey was developed using Google Forms (Appendix B). It was distributed to the community via multiple channels: our Slack workspace, our community mailing lists, our newsletter, and our social media accounts. The initial request was made on 17 October, with an initial closing date of 12 November. Reminders were sent out on all channels a week before closing and the day before closing. The closing date was extended until 14 November to be included in the upcoming monthly Instructor meeting hosted on that same day. We received 200 responses to the community survey. It is difficult to identify a response rate without an exact count of the number of active community members. However, this represents 5% of the members of The Carpentries Slack workspace and 7% of those subscribed to our newsletter.

Findings

In the following sections, we provide a summary of the data available to address each of our evaluation questions.

Survey Respondents: Current Engagement and Demographics

A series of questions were asked to know who within the community responded to the survey. It is important that the findings, and therefore recommendations, included in this report be considered in the context of who was included in the analysis.

When asked how they have engaged with the Carpentries community over the past year, the highest percentage of responses (N = 551 for 200 respondents) indicated that they taught at a Carpentries workshop (18%), attended a Carpentries event (14%), or helped at a workshop (12%; Figure 1). Less than 5% of respondents have served as a Trainer (4%), served on a Committee or Task Force (3%), hosted community programming sessions (2%), served in leadership for a Carpentries subcommunity (2%), or served on the Carpentries Executive Council (<1%; Figure 1).

Figure 1. Percentage of respondents (N = 200 with 551 total responses) who engaged in the community activities listed. Respondents could select more than one category.

We also asked respondents to indicate, on average, how much time they spend on Carpentries-related activities each month. This question was initially intended to help us better understand differences in experience based on level of engagement, but we did not have time to do those analyses. We did learn that most respondents (36%) contributed between one to four hours a month (Figure 2). While 13% indicated not being active in the past year, 7.5% indicated contributing more than ten hours a month (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Percentage of respondents (N = 200) indicating the average time (in hours) spent on Carpentries-related activities each month.

As a global community, it is important to consider the needs and priorities of all of our members. Therefore, we asked questions for respondents to indicate their approximate time zone and preferred language for participating in a community like The Carpentries. Our findings demonstrated that a majority of respondents reported being in UTC -5 (17.5%) which extends across eastern North America and the west coast of South America and UTC +1 (14%) which includes central Europe and Africa (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Percentage of respondents (N=200) by UTC time zone.

When asking respondents about their preferred language for participating in a community like The Carpentries, 181 indicated English followed by 8 indicating Spanish, 4 German, and 2 Italian (Table 2). There were six other languages mentioned once (Table 2). Please note that the survey was only distributed in English, so this sample only represents people comfortable responding in English.

Table 2. Preferred language of respondents. Respondents could indicate more than one language.

Preferred Language	Count	Percentage of Respondents
English	181	91%
Spanish	8	8%
German	4	4%
Italian	2	1%
Arabic	1	<1%
Bangla	1	<1%
French	1	<1%
Afrikaans	1	<1%

Preferred Language	Count	Percentage of Respondents
Dutch	1	<1%
Portuguese	1	<1%
Not Applicable	14	7%

Motivations to Contribute

In addition to understanding how survey respondents are currently engaging with the organisation, we also wanted to understand what motivates them to engage. We asked respondents to complete the following sentence: “I participate in the Carpentries community because...” We then categorised the responses (N=161) to identify primary themes surrounding motivations to contribute to the Carpentries community. The most common themes included: service / giving back (37%), gaining knowledge and skills (32%), shared mission / values (27%), and brings joy / happiness (25%; Table 3). Within the professional development and building institutional categories, there were two responses indicating that participation in the community was a job requirement.

Table 3. Frequency and percentage of responses to the question “I participate in the Carpentries community because”, categorised by theme. Example quotes for the types of responses placed into each category are included. Some responses were placed into more than one theme category.

Theme Category	Frequency of Responses	Percentage of Responses (N=161)	Example Quote
Service / Giving back	59	37%	“As someone who didn't think they were capable of writing code for the majority of their life, I want to make these skills and tools accessible to people like me.”
Gain knowledge and skills	52	32%	“I learn so many teaching and programming skills.”
Shared mission / values	43	27%	“It is a values-driven organisation aligned with my own, and seeks to create positive impacts at a global scale.”
Brings joy / happiness	40	25%	“I enjoy facilitating workshops and trying new things.”
Community /	27	17%	“I love the sense of community and donating

Theme Category	Frequency of Responses	Percentage of Responses (N=161)	Example Quote
belongingness			“My time and skills for such a good and timely cause”
Professional and career development	16	10%	“Professional development, networking, and opportunities for professional service.”
Build institutional capacity	13	8%	“It helps me provide resources to my university and feel empowered as an educator.”
Networking	9	6%	“It is an opportunity to share my knowledge and skills with learners, share ideas and experiences with other Instructors and just to engage in conversation with like-minded folks.”
Gain confidence / self efficacy	7	4%	“It helps me provide resources to my university and feel empowered as an educator.”
Community collaboration / co-creation	7	4%	“I like the difference we all make together. I have found some great collaborators through The Carpentries.”
Quality of Carpentries pedagogy and curriculum	7	4%	“I believe that anyone can learn anything, and The Carpentries provide amazing starters to do so in challenging subjects”
Feel appreciated	2	1%	“I feel that my contributions are valued and helps me gain technical and collaboration skills.”

Additional questions on the community survey addressed participant motivations (Appendix A). Survey respondents indicated agreement in varying degrees with the following relevant statements: I intend to stay engaged with The Carpentries community over the next year (91%), participation in The Carpentries is worth my time (89%), and I feel my contributions to the community are valued (75%; Figure 4). When asked if personal goals for participating are being met 68% agreed while 12% disagreed (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Percentage of respondents (N varies) indicating to what extent they agreed with statements relevant to their motivations to engage.

Experience and Satisfaction

A significant indicator of experience and satisfaction within the community is the Net Promoter Score (NPS). This score asked respondents how likely they are to recommend getting involved with The Carpentries to a friend or colleague on a scale of 0 to 10. Respondents scoring from 0 to 6 are labelled “detractors.” Detractors are believed to be less likely to recommend getting involved and may speak negatively of the organisation. Those who respond with a score of 9 to 10 are labelled “promoters.” Promoters are considered highly likely to recommend getting involved and are enthusiastic about the organisation. Respondents between 7 and 8 are labelled “passives.” Passives are considered indifferent to the potential of becoming a Promoter or Detractor. An NPS above 20 is considered favourable and higher than 30 is excellent. Using this method, the NPS was calculated at 64 (= 71% promoters - 7% detractors; Figure 5).

Figure 5. Percentage of respondents (N = 198) identified as detractors, passives, or promoters based on the Net Promoter Score.

Culture and Values

Several questions on the community survey addressed community culture and our values as an organisation (Appendix A). Survey respondents indicated agreement in varying degrees with the following statements relevant to their experience: The Carpentries provides a welcoming environment (94%), The Carpentries provides a supportive environment (93%), I feel comfortable participating in the community (87%), I belong in The Carpentries (79%), and events are equally accessible to everyone who wants to participate (72%; Figure 6). Eight percent of respondents disagreed with the statement that Carpentries events are equally accessible (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Percentage of respondents (N varies) indicating to what extent they agreed with statements relevant to The Carpentries culture.

Professional and Career Development

The community survey asked respondents how strongly they agreed with statements relevant to how engagement in the community supported their professional and career development. Of those who responded, 88% agreed that participation has helped them develop new skills and 73% agreed that participation helped them meet new colleagues while only 54% indicated that participation helped them reach their career goals (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Percentage of respondents (N varies) indicating to what extent they agreed with statements relevant to professional and career development.

Scaffolding Support

The Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement (CSCCE) defines scaffolding as “the supportive information, activities, and processes that address barriers to member participation and ensure that all members can access and engage in community programming.”¹ Therefore, we asked several questions related to the scaffolding provided to community members to support service in our community roles. Responses indicated that 86% agreed that they know how to find and register for upcoming events, 77% agreed that they can easily find resources to support their participation, and 77% agreed that they feel prepared to serve in their roles in The Carpentries (Figure 8).

¹ Woodley, L., Pratt, K., & Santistevan, C. (2022). The CSCCE Community Participation Model - Scaffolding to lower barriers to participation in STEM communities. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6078934>

Figure 8. Percentage of respondents (N varies) indicating to what extent they agree with statements relevant to the scaffolding support provided for service in community roles.

Collaboration Tools

As an open science community, The Carpentries strives to adopt primarily open-source tools for use by the community. We wanted to gauge the community's satisfaction with the tools available for use by the community to collaborate. Tools and their applications listed in our survey included the AMY database, CodiMD, Etherpad (for note taking), Etherpad (for signing up for events), GitHub, and Zoom. GitHub and Zoom had the highest rates of satisfaction, with 84% and 81%, respectively (Figure 9). The AMY database and Etherpad, when used for note taking, each had a satisfaction rate of around 70% (Figure 9). Use of CodiMD for notetaking and Etherpad for signing up for events, received the lowest satisfaction scores with 55% and 62% satisfaction, respectively (Figure 9). There was also some dissatisfaction related to use of CodiMD for note taking (9%), Etherpad for note taking (8%), and use of Etherpad for signing up to attend Community Sessions or teaching demos (12%; Figure 9). Please note the shifts in sample size related to these tools as many respondents select "NA" if it was a tool they did not use (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Percentage of respondents (N varies) indicating to what extent they are satisfied with the collaboration tools used at The Carpentries.

Communications

We asked several questions to better understand respondents' satisfaction with communications and tools used for communications. When asked about communications from the Core Team and support from the Core Team, respondents indicated 80% and 74% satisfaction, respectively (Figure 10). Communication tools listed in our survey included Slack and TopicBox, with 64% and 45% satisfaction (Figure 10). Thirteen percent of respondents indicated dissatisfaction with Slack, which was high compared to other tools (Figures 9-10). Please note the shifts in sample size related to these tools and many respondents select "NA" if it was a tool they did not use (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Percentage of respondents (N varies) indicating to what extent they are satisfied with communications.

Opportunities for Engagement

Survey respondents indicated satisfaction in varying degrees with the following statements relevant to the opportunities to engage in the organisation: availability of opportunities to participate in their preferred language (76%), opportunities to interact with other community members (68%), availability of programming and events in their time zone (58%), and ratio of synchronous to asynchronous opportunities to participate (61%; Figure 11). There was dissatisfaction with opportunities to interact (7%), availability of synchronous/asynchronous options (7%), and availability of programming and events in my time zone (11%; Figure 11).

Figure 11. Percentage of respondents (N varies) indicating to what extent they are satisfied with opportunities to engage in the community.

Community Reciprocity

Through the survey, we were interested in how we can facilitate community reciprocity, providing opportunities for community members to learn from the community while also sharing their expertise. To that end, we asked:

- What do you hope to gain as a member of the Carpentries community over the next year?
- What do you hope to give back as a member of the Carpentries community over the next year?

We then categorised the responses to identify themes. For the question on what respondents hoped to gain, they reported most wanting to learn and improve skills (33%), to gain teaching experience (18%), and to meet new people, network, and be part of the community (16%; Table 4). For the question on what they hoped to give, they reported most wanting to teach workshops (29%), develop lessons (17%), and support lesson maintenance (13%; Table 5).

Table 4. Frequency and percentage of responses to the question “What Do You Hope to Gain?”, categorised by theme. Some responses were placed into more than one theme category.

Theme Category	Frequency of Responses	Percentage of Responses (N=137)
Learn and improve skills	45	33%
Teaching experience	25	18%
Meet new people / Networking / Be part of community	22	16%
Not sure / NA / Nothing / I plan to step back	14	10%
Collaboration opportunities / Interesting projects to get involved in	11	8%
Materials and resources (including access to good quality lessons)	10	7%
Increased capacity at my institution / local community / region / language	9	7%
Get more involved / Participate more in general	8	6%
Contribute to lessons and resources	7	5%
Support The Carpentries (memberships, spread the word, meet community needs, etc.)	7	5%
Get a job / New job prospects	4	3%
Confidence / empowerment	4	3%
Acknowledgement and recognition (A record of service activities that I can list on my CV)	3	2%
General satisfaction / Service / Giving back	3	2%
Repository Maintainer experience	3	2%

Table 5. Frequency and percentage of responses to the question “What Do You Hope to Give?”, categorised by theme. Some responses were placed into more than one theme category.

Theme Category	Frequency of Responses	Percentage of Responses (N=147)
Teach workshops	43	29%
Lesson development	25	17%
Support lesson maintenance	19	13%
Knowledge exchange	18	12%
Organise / support workshops	16	11%
Community support	14	10%
Raise awareness of / grow organisation	14	10%
Maintainer	11	7%
Time	10	7%
Mentor	10	7%
Trainer	9	6%
Serve on committee / task force	5	3%
Not sure / unclear	4	3%
Feedback	2	1%
Localisation / translation	2	1%

New Programming / Resources

Having explored the experience of our community with existing forms of support and activity, we also wanted to know what people felt we were missing. We asked:

- What additional types of support (e.g., programming or resources) do you wish The Carpentries provided?

We then categorised the responses to identify themes.

The most frequently wished-for areas of support included new lessons (23%), more skill-up sessions (12%) and easier to find resources (10%; Table 6). However, the fourth most popular theme reflected satisfaction with existing support (Table 6).

Table 6. Frequency of responses to the question “What additional types of support (e.g., programming or resources) do you wish The Carpentries provided?”, categorised by theme. Some responses were placed into more than one theme category. Subcategories are also noted for each theme category with frequency of responses shown in parentheses.

Theme Category	Frequency of Responses	Percentage of Responses (N=83)	Subcategories
New lessons	19	23%	Intermediate/advanced training (5) General teacher training (1) Machine learning (1) SQL (1) Public library content (1) HPC (1) Data infrastructure (1) Containers (1) Julia (1) Variants of existing lessons (1) Design patterns (1) Profiling and optimisation (1)
More skill-up sessions	10	12%	Help with GitHub (3) Instructor continuing education (2) How to collaborate (1) Personal development/leadership (1)
Make resources easier to find	8	10%	Responses that asked for this directly (3) Responses requesting resources that do exist but are (implicitly) too hard to find (5)
Nothing	7	8%	Can't think of anything (2) Existing support is enough (5) does not include empty, “NA” or “don't know”
Funding or compensation	6	7%	Local event funding (2) Compensation (monetary or other) (2)
Maintenance support	5	6%	More guides/documentation (2) More Maintainers (1) PR review (1) Meetups (1)

Theme Category	Frequency of Responses	Percentage of Responses (N=83)	Subcategories
Connections	5	6%	Local meetups (3) Match-making around common goals (1) Co-Instructors (1)
Peripheral support for lessons or workshops	5	6%	Alternative datasets (1) AI assistance in workshops (1) Guide for self-organising workshops (1) Easier to report self-organised workshops (1)
Lesson development support	4	5%	Binder instances for Incubator lessons (1) Workbench transition for incubator lessons (1) Documentation / guides (1)
Instructor onboarding support	4	5%	Lesson-specific onboarding (2) Helper / Instructor shadow opportunities (1) Setting expectations regarding bias within instructional teams (1)
Support for individual volunteers	4	5%	Documentation/arguments for employers (2) Instructional roles with reduced time commitment (1) More time zone options (1)
Languages	3	4%	Translation support (2) Materials/examples in Spanish (1)
Support for members/community organisers	2	2%	More membership tracking tools (1) Direct support for upcoming communities (1)
Newsletter	1	1%	
Access to coding tools (e.g. GitHub autopilot)	1	1%	
More in-person training	1	1%	
Recorded lessons	1	1%	

“Warm Fuzzies” from the Additional Comments Section

We loved reading all of the additional comments in this survey! Critical comments were shared as feedback directly to the Core Team separately from this report. Here we present a selection of the detailed praise that we - and you! - received.

“Everyone that I have met in Carpentries has been wonderful. “

“Very thankful to everyone who contributes at every level!”

“Looking for a place to learn, grow, meet amazing people and have fun all at the same time? Join the Carpentries Community. This is my experience and I love it here!”

“So glad I was able to get involved!”

“The community is welcoming and well organized. It hits the sweet spot for having sufficient and targeted staff support to enable volunteer contributions.”

“I think The Carpentries is amazing, keep doing what you're doing!”

“It a wonderful community and everyone is welcome”

“Support from the Core Team is consistently outstanding.”

“I really think The Carpentries is a great organization and is doing great things. I'm excited about the initiatives to deliver Carpentries materials in non-English languages and in less wealthy countries.”

“love ya buckets <3”

“Thank you for all you do on the benefit of the world education :)”

“It's good for my soul :-)”

“I love this community!”

“I am excited to get started!”

Conclusions and Recommendations

It is important to note that the conclusions and recommendations of this report are shaped by the people who participated in the survey, and conversely, by those who did not participate. As noted in the Introduction, the respondents to this survey likely represent between 5 and 10% of The Carpentries community, and an unknown percentage of currently active community members. Future improvements to The Carpentries database may make it possible to improve estimations of the true response rate for this survey.

About this Report

The community survey was meant to serve as an annual check-in on the health of the community and to ensure the work of the organisation was being driven by the community's needs and priorities. Specifically, findings from the survey would allow us to understand the community's motivations to engage, how to improve the volunteer experience, and how to better support participants in meeting personal and professional goals. However, in the first year of the survey's release, [a significant transition occurred within the Core Team](#) that limited its ability to conduct a comprehensive analysis and report on all the data collected. This report includes a complete set of response summaries and a preliminary analysis regarding significance of results. Future analyses could build on this report, for example, by breaking down data by subgroups or expanding upon interpretation of responses presented here.

Sampling Bias

When considering questions about engagement and satisfaction with the community in particular (e.g. Figure 4), it is worth noting that highly engaged community members are expected to be over-represented in the responding population. The majority of respondents also appear to be primarily English speakers residing in North America, South America, Europe, and Africa based on the time zone data collected. This is likely influenced, in part, by the fact that the survey was only distributed in English. Findings and subsequent recommendations will largely represent the views and needs of those groups.

Furthermore, it is worth recognising that responses and requests specific to less common Carpentries roles or regional communities are expected to be under-represented in a survey of the entire community. Future analyses may wish to evaluate responses in proportion to subcommunity representation. We additionally recommend targeted outreach to Carpentries subcommunities less represented in this report before making significant programmatic changes.

In future iterations of the community survey, it is recommended to distribute the survey in multiple languages where possible. The Carpentries Technology Team has activated an account via CrowdIn following conversations with members of the localisation subcommunity who have been testing this as a tool in other communities (e.g, The Turing Way, Bioconductor). CrowdIn is a platform that supports translation of written content and integrates well with AI tools and GitHub. Although initially considered as a tool for adoption by our community to support lesson translations, it has great potential in providing an opportunity for the community to support distribution of communications, and a future community survey, in additional languages.

Professional Development Opportunities

Respondents overwhelmingly value learning and skill development as the primary benefit they receive through participation. This is evident both in questions about motivation and about community reciprocity. Because our community does not, by and large, include learners at our workshops, this emphasises the significance of volunteer participation as a learning experience.

This information is potentially valuable in highlighting the benefits of participation to new volunteers, but also for planning around community succession. When learning is a primary motivation, volunteers may move on if and when that learning experience reaches a plateau. This finding is also consistent with a widespread request for more skill-up sessions (Table 6).

Given these findings, it is recommended that The Carpentries continue to offer more professional development opportunities to whatever extent is possible given reduced Core Team capacity. In particular, supporting community members to organise and offer their own skill-ups could be especially fruitful as this will support programming outside of Core Team availability and also provide opportunities for service and giving back, a primary motivator for survey respondents. New lesson materials were by far the most frequent request, reinforcing the importance of The Carpentries Incubator in paving the road to meet a widespread demand for greater breadth of content.

Accessibility of Programming and Services

There were some notable differences between scores on how **welcoming** (94% agreed; Figure 6) our community is compared to how **accessible** (72% agreed; Figure 6) it is. When asked, 8% of respondents disagreed that Carpentries events are equally accessible to everyone in the community. This may relate to the fact that however much we may emphasise accessible approaches in our programming, ultimately we remain very constrained to locations with robust and affordable internet connections. While there is always more that can be done, it is important to note that the two-year position (2022-2023) of the Accessibility Manager laid the foundations to make the Carpentries resources, programs, and events more accessible. Recommendations to address event accessibility include raising awareness about our Accommodations Policy and how to request accommodations as well as providing additional skill-ups for the community on how to support accessibility in workshops and community events.

Recognition and Appreciation

Results of the survey found that 75% of respondents agreed that their contributions to The Carpentries are valued and less than 1% mentioned appreciation as a reason they contribute to the community. Moving forward, The Carpentries Core Team and Community Coordinators should continue to identify and adopt ways to provide appreciation and recognition for community members. The Community Development Team has drafted a recognition and appreciation plan that will be considered as part of the transition planning.

Consider Motivations

We now have data that provides information on what motivates members of the community to engage. With service as the top motivator, it is important that barriers to serve are broken down through scaffolding resources as well as skill-ups that support members serving in various community roles. While 87% indicated feeling comfortable participating in the community, only 54% indicated that participation helped them reach their career goals.

Collaboration and Communication Tools

Platforms adopted by the organisation for collaboration and communication show varying degrees of use and satisfaction. Offering skill-ups and developing quick start guides would increase awareness of the tools used and support the community in adopting and using platforms they may not be familiar with. The Core Team should also continuously review existing platforms and consider alternatives that could better meet the needs of the community as needs evolve.

Appendices

Appendix A: The Carpentries Theory of Change

View full [Carpentries Theory of Change](#)

Theory of Change Overview

Workshops & Instruction

Curriculum Development

Community Building

Business & Internal

Appendix B: 2023 Community Survey

Thank you for participating in the Carpentries community in 2023!

We would like feedback on your experience as a community member to better understand the benefits you get from your participation and to inform areas of improvement. All the responses collected from the survey will be summarised and shared back with the community in an annual report describing community health.

For support completing this survey, please complete our [accommodations request form](#).

If you have any questions, please contact the Community Development Team at community@carpentries.org.

We are collecting and processing personal data collected with this form in accordance with our [Privacy Policy](#).

How have you been involved in the Carpentries community within the past year? Select all that apply.

- Attended a Carpentries event
- Attended a Workshop as a learner
- Contributed to lesson materials or Glosario
- Served as a Helper at a workshop
- Hosted Community programming sessions (e.g., Community Discussions, Skill-ups)
- Served as a workshop organiser or host
- Taught at a Carpentries workshop (certified or not)
- Served as a Maintainer on a Carpentries repository
- Served as a Trainer (e.g., Instructor Trainer or Curriculum Development Trainer)
- Served on another Carpentries committee or task force (e.g., Curriculum Advisory Committee, Code of Conduct Committee)
- Served in leadership for a Carpentries subcommunity
- Served on The Carpentries Executive Council
- Other

On average, how much time do you spend on Carpentries-related activities each month? We are grateful for all contributions of time and effort. This question is only intended to help us better understand differences in experience based on level of engagement.

- I have been inactive within the community in the past year
- Less than 1 hour a month
- 1 to 4 hours a month
- 5 to 10 hours a month
- More than 10 hours a month

Please select how strongly you agree with the following statements on a scale from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 5 (Strongly agree).

- Participation in The Carpentries is worth my time.
- My personal goals for participating in The Carpentries are being met.
- I intend to stay engaged with The Carpentries over the next year.
- I feel prepared to serve in my role in The Carpentries.
- I know how to find and register for upcoming events and opportunities.
- I can easily find resources available to support my participation in The Carpentries.
- I feel my contributions to the Carpentries community are valued.
- The Carpentries provides a welcoming environment.
- The Carpentries provides a supportive environment.
- I feel Carpentries events are equally accessible to everyone who wants to participate.
- My participation in The Carpentries has helped me develop new skills.
- My participation in The Carpentries has helped me reach my career goals.
- My participation in The Carpentries has helped me meet new colleagues.
- I feel comfortable participating in the Carpentries community.
- I belong in the Carpentries community.

Please provide any comments relative to your above responses.

Please select how satisfied you are with each of the following as it applies to engagement within the Carpentries community. Please select on a scale from 1 (Not at all satisfied) to 5 (Extremely satisfied) or not applicable.

- Zoom for virtual meetings and events
- Etherpad for collaborative note taking
- Etherpad for signing up for Community Sessions and Teaching Demos
- CodiMD for collaborative note taking
- Slack for communications
- TopicBox for mailing lists
- AMY database for tracking participation
- GitHub for collaboration
- Communications from the Core Team
- Support from the Core Team
- Opportunities to interact with other community members
- Ratio of synchronous and asynchronous opportunities to participate
- The availability of programming and events in my timezone
- The availability of opportunities to participate in my preferred language(s)

Please provide any comments relative to your above responses.

What time zone are you in?

What is your preferred language for participating in a community like The Carpentries?

Please provide any comments relative to your above response.

I participate in The Carpentries community because _____.

What do you hope to gain as a member of the Carpentries community over the next year?

What do you hope to give back as a member of the Carpentries community over the next year?

What additional types of support (e.g., programming or resources) do you wish The Carpentries provided?

How likely are you to recommend getting involved with The Carpentries to a friend or colleague?
[Net promoter score]

Please provide any additional comments relevant to your experience as a member of The Carpentries community.

Thanks for providing input on your experience as a member of the Carpentries community!